

RISK FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF GALLSTONE DISEASE AFTER BARIATRIC SURGERY

Atakhanov I.K.
Khakimov D.M.
Botirov A.K.
Botirov J.A.

Andijan State Medical Institute
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18473143>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 29st January 2026

Accepted: 30th January 2026

Online: 31th January 2026

KEYWORDS

Aim of the study. To identify risk factors contributing to the development of gallstone disease after bariatric surgery

ABSTRACT

Modern literature indicates a wide variability in the timing of gallstone disease (GSD) manifestation, especially in patients with morbid obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), with the frequency of repeat surgical interventions reaching 15–30% [1;2]. The relevance of this issue increases in the context of the growing number of bariatric procedures and the expansion of their indications, highlighting the need for new prognostically justified therapeutic and diagnostic algorithms.

Relevance. Modern literature indicates a wide variability in the timing of gallstone disease (GSD) manifestation, especially in patients with morbid obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), with the frequency of repeat surgical interventions reaching 15–30% [1;2]. The relevance of this issue increases in the context of the growing number of bariatric procedures and the expansion of their indications, highlighting the need for new prognostically justified therapeutic and diagnostic algorithms.

Aim of the study. To identify risk factors contributing to the development of gallstone disease after bariatric surgery.

Materials and Methods. The present study was conducted at the private clinics Soglom Avlod and SEHAT in Andijan during the period from 2023 to 2025. A total of 1,337 bariatric surgeries were performed during this period, including laparoscopic sleeve gastrectomy (LSG) and one-anastomosis gastric bypass (OAGB), for the treatment of obesity and obesity combined with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Among the 1,337 patients, 102 (7.6%) subsequently developed gallstone disease (GSD) after bariatric surgery, and repeat cholecystectomy was performed in 51 (3.8%) patients, who constituted the core group for risk factor analysis. Accordingly, the study population comprised 102 (7.6%) patients with postoperative GSD. Two groups were defined for comparative purposes:

- **Comparison group** (2023) – 483 patients. GSD subsequently developed in 44 (9.1%) patients, of whom 32 (6.6%) required repeat surgical interventions.

- **Main group** (2024–2025) – 854 patients. GSD subsequently developed in 58 (6.8%) patients, of whom 19 (2.2%) required repeat surgical interventions.

To address the study objectives, clinical, laboratory, instrumental, and statistical methods were applied in accordance with the latest standard methodologies and the examination guidelines approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results of the Study. In the course of the study, we performed a detailed analysis of the outcomes in the comparison group (n = 483) of patients who underwent bariatric surgery according to the traditional approach, in which cholecystectomy (CE) was performed only in the presence of gallstones. Among these 483 patients, 44 (9.1%) subsequently developed gallstone disease (GSD), of whom 32 (72.7%) required repeat surgical intervention. This analysis highlights the limitations of the traditional approach.

To assess the clinical presentation of GSD in the comparison group, a detailed evaluation of key risk factors, comorbidities, and morphological features was conducted. The female-to-male ratio was 28:6, indicating a predominance of males (63.6%). This is consistent with literature data showing that men more frequently have asymptomatic GSD after bariatric surgery. Patients in the comparison group were aged 25–65 years, with the majority between 35 and 50 years, representing an active working-age population for whom GSD-related complications carry significant social and economic implications.

All patients had morbid obesity (class III–IV), confirming the high risk of gallstone disease (GSD) with rapid weight loss following bariatric surgery. Nearly half of the patients, 21 (47.7%), had concomitant type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), which increases bile lithogenicity and the likelihood of stone formation. The preclinical stage of GSD (presence of biliary sludge) was observed in 12 (27.3%) patients, often asymptomatic, preceding the formation of gallstones.

Signs of chronic inflammation (gallbladder wall thickening ≥ 3 mm) were noted in 14 (31.8%) patients, increasing the risk of stone formation in the long term. Mechanical disturbances of bile evacuation (deformation, kinking, signs of stasis) were observed in 11 (25%) patients, contributing to stasis and gallstone formation. Evidence of hypomotor dysfunction of the gallbladder (increased gallbladder volume > 60 mL) and a higher risk of stone formation was found in 9 (20.5%) patients. These data indicate that most cases of GSD developed within the first 6–12 months after bariatric surgery. The presence of T2DM, gallbladder morphological changes, and biliary sludge identifies a high-risk group that was not accounted for in the traditional approach.

Among the 44 patients, 21 (47.7%) did not take Ursophalk (ursodeoxycholic acid), 12 (27.3%) took it for less than 3 months, 8 (18.2%) for 3–6 months, and only 3 (6.8%) for more than 6 months. Thus, nearly half of the patients did not receive Ursophalk, and among those who did, the treatment course was short.

Main Limitations of the Traditional Approach

1. Lack of risk stratification: Patients were considered as a homogeneous group; T2DM, gallbladder morphological changes, and biliary sludge were ignored.
2. Insufficient monitoring of gallbladder morphology: There was no standardized ultrasound assessment or documentation of risk features.
3. Absence of predictive criteria for cholecystectomy (CE): Surgery was performed only in the presence of gallstones.
4. Empirical administration of Ursophalk: Dosage was unregulated, treatment duration was short, and dynamic monitoring was lacking.

5. Increased frequency of repeat surgeries: 72.7% of patients with GSD required repeat intervention, a significant proportion performed emergently.

6. Increased risk of complications: Technical difficulties due to adhesions, thickened gallbladder wall, and deformities; early wound and systemic complications were observed.

7. Lack of individualized treatment: Reduced effectiveness of bariatric therapy and decreased quality of life for patients.

Conclusion.

The retrospective clinical analysis of the comparison group (n = 483; 44 patients developed GSD; 32 required repeat surgeries) demonstrated the limitations of the traditional approach. Performing cholecystectomy only in the presence of gallstones leads to delayed diagnosis of GSD, increased frequency of repeat and emergency surgeries, and higher complication rates. Risk factors were ignored: T2DM, gallbladder morphological changes, and biliary sludge were not considered when planning preventive measures. Empirical prophylaxis with ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) was ineffective. The absence of standardized protocols and monitoring resulted in a high incidence of GSD. Repeat surgeries were complex and unsafe, with adhesions, kinking, and gallbladder wall thickening causing conversions and early postoperative complications.

A systematic approach is therefore required. Only a comprehensive assessment of clinical and morphological factors can reduce the risk of repeat interventions and complications, improving the safety of bariatric surgery. All of the above underscores the need for a systematic modification of the approach to GSD prevention.

References:

1. Gordeev A.O., Konovalov A.N. Cholecystectomy in the structure of repeat surgeries after bariatric treatment of obesity. *Surgery*. 2020;9:25–29.
2. Nosov A.Yu. et al. (conditional source). Analogue: Nosov A.Yu., Trusov D.V. Gallstone disease in patients with obesity and diabetes mellitus: features of the clinical course. *Endoscopic Surgery*. 2023;1:40–45.